

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18110548

On The Structural Properties And Applications Of Antichain Graphs

*Dogondaji A.M. & Adamu I.

Department of Mathematics, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto-Nigeria

*Corresponding Authors Email Address: dogondaji@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study of antichain graphs is important in order to connect order theory, graph theory and combinatorics to model, analyze and solve complex structural problems. This project investigates the structural properties of antichain graph including their connectivity, independence, domination and chromatic characteristics. This is obtained by employing the concept of antichain is partially order set where no two element are comparable to represent and analyzed graphical structure. The research shows the effect of these structural properties determined on the practical application of antichain in graphs in solving complex network problem. Furthermore the research the research provided graphical representation which also demonstrate how the theoretical results are applicable to real life situation.

Keywords: antichain graphs, chromatic number, graph structure and graphical representation

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Graph theory is a central area of discrete mathematics concerned with the study of graphs, which are mathematical structures used to model relationships between objects (West, 2021). An antichain is a concept that arises from order theory, a branch of mathematics dealing with partially ordered sets (posets). In a poset, an antichain is a subset in which no two distinct elements are comparable, meaning that for any two elements and in the set, neither $a \leq b$ nor $b \leq a$ holds (Davey & Priestley, 2002). The importance of antichain graph also lies in their ability to simplify complex relationships. By representing only the non-comparable elements, they reduce the complexity of analyzing large data sets and allow clearer identification of independent structures (Brightwell & Winkler, 1991) this property is particularly beneficial in operations research, combinatorial optimization, and the design of fault tolerant system (West, 2001).

Among the many domains of mathematics graph theory has emerges as a powerful tool for representing and analyzing relationship within sets of object. Graph theory intersect with multiple other area such as combinatorics, logic and algebra offering insight into both theoretical and applied problem. (Murty 2008). The representation of antichains in the form of graphs leads to the concept of antichain graphs, where vertices represent the elements of the antichain and edges encode specific relationships, often based on the underlying poset structure (Biro et al., 2014). Antichain graphs provide a powerful visual and analytical tool for understanding the independence and separation of elements in a system. In these graphs, the absence of comparability ensures that vertices remain mutually independent, which has important implications in algorithm design, scheduling theory, and parallel computing (Golumbic, 2004). Historically, one of the landmark results in the study of antichains is Sperner's Theorem (Sperner, 1928), which gives the maximum possible size of an antichain in the Boolean lattice. This theorem has deep connections to combinatorics, coding theory, and optimization problems. Another important result is

Dilworth's Theorem (Dilworth, 1950), which connects the size of the largest antichain in a poset to the minimum number of chains needed to cover the set. Both results form part of the theoretical backbone of antichain graph research. Antichain graphs also play a role in comparability graphs and incomparability graphs, where edges indicate whether elements of the poset are comparable or not (Pach&Tóth, 2006). In incomparability graphs, an antichain corresponds to a clique (complete subgraph), meaning every vertex in the subset is adjacent to every other vertex reflecting total incomparability in the poset. This duality between order theory and graph theory enables new insights into network structures, decision processes, and data classification (Trotter, 1992).

In modern applications, antichain graphs are relevant in a variety of fields. For example, in distributed computing, they can represent sets of processes that can be executed in parallel without conflict (Kumar et al., 2018). In bioinformatics, they can be used to model mutually exclusive genetic markers or molecular interactions (Zhao et al., 2017). In information theory, they help optimize non-interfering communication channels (Cover & Thomas, 2006). Due to growing complexity of systems in computer science, engineering, and combinatorial optimization, there is an increasing need to understand the structural properties of antichain graphs and their applications. This understanding can help in designing efficient algorithms for resource allocation, scheduling, network design, and classification problems where non-comparability plays a key role. By studying the interplay between antichain theory and graph representation, researchers can uncover new ways to model independence and avoid conflict in both theoretical and applied contexts (Bonnet et al, 2019).

1.2 Definition of Some Basic Terms

Definition 1.2.1 An antichain in a partially ordered set (Posets) is a subset of element in which no two element are comparable, that is for any two element a and b in the antichain A , neither $a < b$ nor $b < a$ holds. A graph $G=(V,E)$ is said to be an antichain graph if there exist a poset $P=(X,<)$ such that the vertices V is a subset of X and edges E connect only pair of incomparable element in P . Thus each edge (u,v) belongs to E correspond to an antichain relation $u \setminus v$ meaning u and v are incomparable.

Definition 1.2.2 An antichain graph is a subset A is a subset of X of a poset such that every pair of distinct element in A is comparable in the other word no element in the antichain precede or follow another.

Definition 1.2.3 An antichain graph is an undirected graph $G=(V,E)$ where each vertex V belong to V represent an element of a poset

- An edge (u,v) belong to E exist if and only if $U \setminus V$ meaning u and v are incomparable in the underlying poset.

Definition 1.2.4 An antichain is a set of element in a partially ordered set (Poset) such that no two elements are comparable.

Definition 1.2.5 A finite poset is a poset $(X, <)$ where the set X contain a finite number of element in the study we primarily focus on finite poset and their antichain graphs.

Definition 1.2.6 Antichain graphs, a graph representing an antichain, where vertices represent element and edges represent incomparability.

Definition 1.2.7 Comparability graph, a graph that represent a comparability relation of a poset. Antichain graph can be viewed as a graph with no comparability.

Definition 1.2.8 Poset (Partially ordered set) a set together with partial order. Antichain are defined based on posets.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the research will consider the various method, of formation of antichain graphs and their structures, it begins as follow;-

3.2 Antichain graphs of poset.

Example 1.1 consider the graph of the poset below

Fig (i) Antichain graph

An antichain in this poset is described as the set $\{b,c,d,e\}$, the edges of b,c,dans e are all incomparable (ther is no relation between any pair of them).

- b to c are antichain because there is no any relation between them, its antichain
- d to e are antichain because they are incomparable
- a to f are antichain because ther is no any relation between them its antichain.

Example 1.2

Fig (ii) Antichain graph

An antichain in this poset is described the set $\{b,c,d,e,f,g\}$, the edges of b,c,d,e,f and g are all incomparable (there is no any relation between any pair of them).

- b to c is an antichain because there is no any relation on between them.

- d to e is an antichain because there is no any pair of them.
- f to g is an antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- a to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- a to f are antichain because there is no any relation between them.

Example 1.3

Fig (iii) Antichain graph

An antichain in this poset is described the set $\{c,d,e,f,a\}$, the edges of c,d,e,f,a are all incomparable (there is no relation between any pair of them).

- a to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them, its antichain.
- d to e are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- e to f is an antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- a to f are antichain because there is no any pair of them.
- c to f are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- f to a are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- e to b are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- c to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- e to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them.

Example 1.4

Fig (iv) Antichain graph

An anti chain in this poset is described as the set $\{b,c,a,e\}$, the edges of b,c, a,e are all in comparable (there is no relation between any pair of them).

- b to c are antichain because because there is no any relation between them its antichain

- c to e, are antichain because there is no any pair of them
- a to d, are antichain because there is no any pair of them

Example 1.5

Fig (v) Antichain graph

An antichain in this poset is described as the set (a, b, c, d, e, f) , the edges of a, b, c, d, e, f are all incomparable. (there is no relation between any pair of them)

- a to b are antichain because there is no any pair of them
- b to c are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- d to c are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- e to f are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- a to c are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- d to f are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- a to f are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- d to c are antichain because there is no any relation between them.

Example 1.6

Fig (vi) Antichain graph

An antichain of this poset is described as the set (b, c, d, e) , the edges of b, c, d, e , are all incomparable (there is no any relation between them)

- b to c are antichain because there is no any relation between them
- d to e are antichain because there is no any relation between them
- a to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them

Example 1.7

An empty graph is a graph with no edges or vertices it's a graph that has no nodes and no connection between them. Since an empty graph has no edges between any two vertices (either because there are no vertices or no edges), it's an example of antichain graph. An empty graph is indeed on example of an antichain graph.

Example 1.8

Fig (vii) Antichain graph

An antichain of its poset is described as the set (b c a d e), the edges of b c, d a e are all incomparable (there is no rotation between any pair of them)

- b to c are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- a to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them.
- d to e are antichain because there is no any relation between them.

Example 1.9

Fig (viii) Antichain graph

An antichain of this poset is described as the set of (a b c d), the edges of a,b,c,d are all incomparable (because there is no any relation between them).

- a to b are antichain because there is no any relation between them
- c to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them

Example 1.10

Fig (ix) Antichain graph

An antichain of this poset is described as the set $(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)$ the edges of $a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i$ are all incomparable because (because there is no any relation between them)

- a to b are antichain because there is no any relation between them
- c to d are antichain because there is no any relation between them
- f to g are antichain because there is no any relation between them
- h to i are antichain because there is no any relation between them
- d to e are antichain because there is no any relation between them

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Proposition 3.3.1

In any finite poset, the size of the largest antichain is equal to the minimum number of chains into which the poset can be partitioned

Proof

Let $P = (X, \leq)$ be a finite partially ordered set (poset) then the size of the largest antichain in P is equal to the minimum number of chain needed to cover X .

Lemma 3.2.1 (Dilworth 1995) This Lemma state that a poset can be partitioned into antichain if and only if its height is less that or equal to t

Proposition 3.3.2

Mirsky's theorem (Dual of Dilworth's theorem) in partially ordered set (poset), the maximum size of a chain (a totally ordered subset) is equal to the minimum number of antichains (subset where no two element are comparable) needed to cover the poset.

proof

Let P be a partially ordered set, then $\text{Max}(|C|; C \text{ is a chain in } P) = \text{min}(|A|; A \text{ is an antichain cover of } P)$

REFERENCES

- Aharoni, R., & Berger, E. (2011). Strongly maximal antichains in posets. *Discrete Mathematics*, 311(15), 1518–1522.
- Atminas, A., Brignall, R., Lozin, V., & Stacho, J. (2021). Minimal classes of graphs of unbounded clique-width defined by finitely many forbidden induced subgraphs. *Discrete Applied Mathematics*, 295, 57–69.

- Balogh, J., Morris, R., & Samotij, W. (2015). Independent sets in hypergraphs. *Journal of the American Mathematical Society*, 28(3), 669–709.
- Blinovsky, V. M., & Harper, L. H. (2002). Size of the largest antichain in a partition poset. *Problems of Information Transmission*, 38, 347–353.
- Bollobás, B. (1986). *Combinatorics: Set Systems, Hypergraphs, Families of Vectors and Combinatorial Probability*. Cambridge University Press.
- Bollobás, B., & Thomason, A. (1995). Projections of bodies and hereditary properties of hypergraphs. *Bulletin of the London Mathematical Society*, 27(5), 417–424.
- Chase, Z. (2020). Antichains in the Boolean lattice and the container method. *Electronic Journal of Combinatorics*, 27(4), P4.
- Duffus, D., & Rival, I. (1980). Graph-theoretical properties of ordered sets: the dimension of an order and the width of its comparability graph. *SIAM Journal on Algebraic Discrete Methods*, 1(2), 151–160.
- Erdős, P., & Moser, L. (1964). On the representation of directed graphs as unions of orderings. *Publ. Math. Inst. Hung. Acad. Sci.*, 9, 125–132.
- Erdős, P., & Spencer, J. (1974). *Probabilistic Methods in Combinatorics*. Academic Press.
- Foldes, S., & Woodroffe, R. (2011). Antichain cutsets of strongly connected posets. arXiv preprint arXiv:1109.5705.
- Green, R. M., & Xu, T. (2024). A partial order on antichains of a fixed size. arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.06732.
- Hausdorff, U., & Bonnet, R. (1999). Hausdorff's theorem for posets that satisfy the finite antichain property. *Fundamenta Mathematicae*, 159(1), 51–69.
- Ignatov, D. I. (2023). A note on the number of (maximal) antichains in the lattice of set partitions. In *Graph-Based Representation and Reasoning, Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, Springer, Cham.
- Kleitman, D. J. (1969). On Dedekind's problem: the number of monotone Boolean functions. *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, 21(3), 677–682.
- Lieby, P. (2005). Antichains on three levels. *The Electronic Journal of Combinatorics*, 11(1), Article R50.
- Michael, J. (2017). Antichain toggling and rowmotion. arXiv preprint arXiv:1709.09331.
- Moshkovitz, M., & Shapira, A. (2018). Exact bounds for some hypergraph problems via the container method. *Combinatorica*, 38(1), 75–109.
- Noel, J. A., Scott, A., & Sudakov, B. (2016). Supersaturation in posets and applications involving the container method. arXiv preprint arXiv:1610.01521.
- Postnikov, A. (2006). Total positivity, Grassmannians, and networks. *Mathematics Research Letters*, 13(5-6), 817–836.
- Sapozhenko, A. A. (1991). On the number of antichains in multilevelled ranked posets. *Discrete Mathematics and Applications*, 1(2), 149–160.
- Sapozhenko, A. A. (1991). The number of antichains in ranked posets. *Discrete Mathematics and Applications*, 1(1), 35–47.
- Schrijver, A. (2003). *Combinatorial Optimization: Polyhedra and Efficiency*. Springer-Verlag.
- Shahistha, Hanif, & Arathi Bhat, K. (2025). Determinant of Antichain Graphs. *Global and Stochastic Analysis*, 12(1), 21–28.
- Shahistha, K., Arathi Bhat, K., & Sudhakara, G. (2021). Antichain Graphs. *IAENG International Journal of Applied Mathematics*, 51(3), 1–7.
- Shearer, J. B. (1985). A note on the independence number of triangle-free graphs. *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society*, 95(2), 273–278.
- Stanford, R. P. (2005). On complexity of some chain and antichain partition problems. In *Graph-Theoretic Concepts in Computer Science (WG '91)*, 97–104.
- Stanley, R. P. (2011). *Enumerative Combinatorics, Volume 1*